

DECIPHER

Holistic decision-making for climate & environment

D1.2 Series of Target Workshops

Learnings and Project Takeaways

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LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym	Long text
WP	Work package

1. Stakeholder engagement strategy and targeted workshops

DECIPHER's central aim is to develop, in conjunction with stakeholders, an innovative decision-making framework for policymaking in spheres of climate, biodiversity and sustainability. DECIPHER's partners are geographically dispersed across Europe, which has allowed it to engage with a wide range of expert stakeholders. These engagements have given DECIPHER partners an understanding of the best practices in the relevant fields and provided an opportunity to share the outputs of DECIPHER workstreams with critical stakeholders.

DECIPHER has made use of its network of expert stakeholders to host a series of six targeted workshops directly related to the project work packages. These include empirical policy evaluation (WP2), modelling of ecosystem services (WP3), innovative economic methods in modelling (WP4), novel decision-making frameworks (WP5), the design of a stakeholder engagement tool (WP6), and the role of sustainability criteria in university curricula (WP7). Work package 1 covers the stakeholder engagement and therefore does not have a dedicated workshop associated with it.

D1.2, this document, details, for each workshop the specific stakeholder community that was targeted depended on the aims of the workshop in question. Section 2 covers these details. The next steps for the project are provided in section 3.

2. Targeted Workshops

Work Package 2: Empirical Policy Evaluation

Date: 26/11/2024

Concept

The WP2 workshop on ex-post policy evaluation aimed to gather a balanced group of climate, energy, and environmental policymakers from EU, national, and local levels, with a particular focus on those working on heating decarbonisation. The workshop sought to explore how policymakers evaluate the success of implemented policies ex-post and how these evaluations can be better integrated with modelling for climate, energy, and

environmental policymaking. Key objectives included identifying the methods used for policy evaluation, examining gaps in current approaches, and considering how modelling can support more effective and legitimate policy assessments.

Attendees

Table 1. Work Package 2 Workshop Attendees

Organisation	Number of Attendees
European Environment Agency (EEA)	2
Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD)	1
Concito	1
Energy Cities	1
DG ENER, European Commission	1
World Resources Institute	1
German Energy Agency (dena)	1

Discussion

The workshop opened with an overview of the DECIPHER project. The ensuing discussion highlighted the role of economic and integrated assessment models in ex-ante climate policy appraisal and empirical policy evaluation. A case study on EU Structural Funds provided insight into the varying effectiveness of these funds in reducing emissions, emphasizing the need for tailored policy approaches. The debate also touched on the political use of economic modelling in policymaking, noting how models serve both as a tool for legitimizing predetermined targets and as a mechanism for informing policy design.

Participants shared insights from their respective fields, discussing challenges in policy evaluation, particularly concerning additionality, behavioural responses to policies, and data gaps in assessing building energy efficiency. Case studies, such as the Netherlands' approach to natural gas phase-out in buildings, provided practical examples of policy implementation complexities. The discussion also underscored the role of one-stop shops and minimum energy performance standards as potential policy instruments, while acknowledging the barriers posed by market failures, transaction costs, and knowledge gaps. Various EU-level evaluation efforts were mentioned, including assessments of the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) and national energy performance databases.

Project Takeaways

Key takeaways for the project include the importance of evaluating both quantitative and qualitative aspects of policy effectiveness, particularly regarding the real-world impact of policy measures. The workshop identified the need for improved methodologies to assess the additionality of funding mechanisms, as well as the behavioural and market dynamics influencing policy outcomes. Several promising case studies were proposed for further investigation, including localized policy approaches, the scaling-up of best practices, and the role of financial and information-based interventions. Moving forward, the project will incorporate these insights into its research design, with a focus on refining evaluation criteria and ensuring that policy assessments capture both economic and social dimensions.

Work Package 3: Advancing Coastal Wetlands as Nature-based Solutions

Date: 13/11/2024

Concept

The WP3 workshop on wetlands valuations aimed to gather national and EU policymakers, environmental NGOs, and researchers working on environmental assessment, ecosystem valuation, and nature-based solutions for coastal adaptation. The workshop focused on methodologies for evaluating coastal wetlands and their ecosystem services at a global scale, as well as the role of wetlands as nature-based solutions for sea-level rise adaptation. Key objectives included understanding how stakeholders use environmental valuation in policymaking and advocacy, examining existing methodologies for assessing ecosystem services, and identifying how modelling can better support policy and decision-making in environmental assessments and coastal resilience planning.

Attendees

Table 2. Work Package 3 Workshop Attendees

Organisation	Number of Attendees
Institute for European Environmental Policy	1
European Central Bank	1
International Union for Conservation of Nature	1
Europe Jacques Delors	1
Foundation for Sustainable Development	1

RVO Nederland	1
European Investment Bank	1
United Nations Environment Programme	1
European Environment Agency	1
The Green Tank	2
DG CLIMA, European Commission	1
World Meteorological Organisation	1

Discussion

A key part of the discussion was the presentation of the DIVA (Dynamic Interactive Vulnerability Assessment) model, a global-scale coastal impact assessment tool used to evaluate the protective functions of wetlands against sea level rise and extreme flooding events, by DECIPHER researcher Sebastiano Bacca. The research demonstrated the economic benefits of wetlands, both in terms of avoided damages and additional welfare values, emphasizing the importance of incorporating nature-based solutions (NbS) into coastal adaptation strategies. The model integrates biophysical and socio-economic factors, with preliminary results indicating significant cost savings in areas with extensive wetland coverage.

Participants provided insights on the importance of broadening the assessment to include additional ecosystem services such as carbon sequestration, water purification, and biodiversity support. It was highlighted that while the model accounts for multiple services through meta-regression techniques, local-scale studies remain necessary for more granular evaluations. Further discussion explored the challenges of implementing nature-based solutions, particularly the need for a structured financial argument to attract investment. Stakeholders from financial institutions, think tanks, and policy bodies stressed that incorporating cost-benefit analyses, long-term risk mitigation data, and return-on-investment frameworks would enhance the case for NbS. The importance of local stakeholder engagement was also emphasized, with recommendations to integrate landscape approaches and ensure alignment with regulatory and governance structures.

Project Takeaways

The discussion reaffirmed the need for economic valuation tools to support decision-making on nature-based solutions. While global models like DIVA provide a broad policy-level perspective, local specificity remains critical for successful implementation. There is strong demand for more refined cost-benefit analysis, including the profitability of NbS, to improve investment attractiveness. Additionally, the conversation underscored the need

for better integration between financial models and ecosystem service valuation to align public and private sector priorities. Moving forward, the DECIPHER project should explore enhanced sectoral assessments, regulatory considerations, and local adaptation frameworks to ensure that NbS are positioned as viable, cost-effective, and scalable solutions for climate resilience.

Work Package 4: Innovative Economic Methods

Date: 04/03/2025

Concept

The WP4 workshop on *innovative economic methods* aimed to share the latest innovations related to economic decision-making of agents in IAMs developed within DECIPHER with expert stakeholders. The session was designed to bring together thought leaders in integrated assessment modelling, including representatives from sister projects such as PRISMA and IAM COMPACT, as well as policymakers involved in modelling at DG ENER and DG CLIMA. The primary objectives were to present DECIPHER's advancements in economic modelling, gather critical feedback on proposed innovations, and discuss the practical challenges of integrating these developments into existing models.

Attendees

Table 3 Work Package 4 Workshop Attendees

Organisation	Number of Attendees
JRC	2
DG CLIMA	1
DG ENER	2
DG ECFIN	1
DG R&I	1
University Warsaw	3
KTH	1
CMCC	1
UK IMPERIAL	1
NTUA	1

Discussion

Key themes under discussion at the workshop included labour market developments, investment decision processes, and uncertainty quantification in policy modelling. The presentation by Cambridge Econometrics on labour market modelling innovations highlighted the integration of qualifications and occupational shifts over time, using Croatia as a test case to explore skill mismatches and retraining costs. Financing aspects, discussed in the same presentation, focused on updating the cost of capital for renewable technologies (with Germany as case study), testing the implications of financial conditions on technology deployment, and refining approaches to public and private investment financing. Complementing this, the session on investment decision-making introduced models, presented by E3-Modelling, focussed on accounting for capital mobility and rational expectations to enhance investment strategies. The final presentation by University of Exeter on uncertainty quantification emphasized the increasing role of uncertainty in policy modelling, showcasing the use of statistical emulation to assess the robustness of different policy scenarios.

Participants engaged in a discussion on the practical implications of these model innovations, exploring their relevance for labour market forecasting, investment planning, and policy design. Questions focused on the applicability of labour market projections for sectoral workforce needs, particularly in the energy transition, and the feasibility of extending uncertainty modelling through emulation to other economic models beyond those applied in DECIPHER. The discussion also touched on data limitations, classification systems for labour market analysis, and the role of policy levers such as carbon pricing in influencing renewable energy deployment. Stakeholders expressed interest in how these innovations could support decision-making in policy and research, with suggestions for further refinement, including sector-specific applications and broader validation of model assumptions.

Project Takeaways

The insights from this workshop will inform the ongoing development of DECIPHER's economic modelling tools, particularly in refining labour market projections, investment frameworks, and uncertainty quantification methods. The discussions reinforced the importance of integrating dynamic labour market modelling to address skill mismatches and retraining needs for the energy transition. The investment decision-making models will continue to evolve to account for financial conditions and capital mobility, while uncertainty quantification techniques will be further explored to enhance the robustness of policy evaluation frameworks. These findings will contribute to future DECIPHER reports, their dissemination, and stakeholder engagements, ensuring that methodological advancements remain aligned with policy and research needs.

Work Package 5: Decision Making Frameworks

Date: 26/03/2025

Concept

The WP5 workshop on risk and resilience in climate, disaster, and energy policymaking aimed to engage policymakers and experts in a holistic discussion on integrating risk and resilience into decision-making frameworks. The session sought to bring together national experts and EU policymakers, particularly those working on risk assessments and climate adaptation, alongside subject matter experts specializing in systemic risk assessment and modelling. The workshop introduced methodologies such as Risk-Opportunity Analysis, the Triple Dividend Framework for disaster and climate risk management, multi-criteria decision-making, and financial resilience assessment. By examining how risk is incorporated into climate, biodiversity, and energy policymaking, the session aimed to foster a comprehensive approach to resilience that captures both direct and indirect benefits for long-term policy planning.

Attendees

Table 4. Work Package 5 Workshop Attendees

Organisation	Number of Attendees
IIASA	1
Zurich Resilience Solutions	1
ECMWF	1
European Commission DG HERA	1
European Commission - DG ENER	1
Accelerator for Systemic Risk Assessment	1
Foresight Transitions	3
CMCC	1
Climafin	1
Climate analytics	1

SOAS	1
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Discussion

After the presentations on the risk and opportunity analysis framework (Ian Burton, Exeter University), the triple dividend framework (Reinhard Mechler, IIASA), and multi-criteria decision-making framework (Oxana Soimu, Deusto University), various questions were raised. Concerning the risk and opportunity analysis framework, deep uncertainty and the difficulties to modelling such dynamics were discussed. A discussion on the assumptions in the framework, among other related to path dependency, was followed in which caution was raised about not overselling the capacities of the models – while stressing their value in different phases of the policy process (e.g., also ex-ante). Other questions about the triple dividend framework focused on the level at which the modelling takes place (systemic, national, case-based) and how it aligned well with other studies, in addition to questions about whether it is feasible to bring together modelling work to support scenarios for the SDGs, highlighting the importance of incorporating economic models, but also the challenge of the different ‘languages’ that are being spoken in the academic and policy expert communities respectively. A final important point concerned the decision-making architecture in governments, and the way questions related to risks and resilience are being formulated by decisionmakers.

Project Takeaways

Take-aways for the project research among others includes considering careful framing what the work around deep uncertainty and its assumptions. Moreover, it has been raised by several stakeholders that it would be valuable to have national case studies alongside the modelling work. Finally, the value of modelling in different phases of the policy process was stressed in addition to the need to generate more awareness about the triple dividend framework among policymakers. Generally, stakeholders expressed interests in outcomes of the project.

Work Package 6: Stakeholder Engagement Tool

Date: 18/03/2025

Concept

The WP6 workshop on the stakeholder engagement tool aimed to present a beta version of a core output of DECIPHER, an online tool to allow stakeholders to better understand and interpret integrated assessment modelling results. The workshop gathered structured feedback on the tool’s design and usability. The session was designed for technical policy staff, European Commission policy officers, international organizations (OECD, IEA, IRENA), industry associations (Eurelectric, WindEurope, European Roundtable for Industry), and NGOs (Climate Action Network, Friends of Europe). The workshop

provided an interactive demonstration of the tool within the scenario framework developed for policy assessment, inviting participants to assess its relevance and suggest improvements to enhance its effectiveness for decision-making. Moreover, the workshop collected feedback on the relevance of a set of indicators produced in context of the multi-criteria decision making framework to be integrated in IAMs.

Attendees

Table 5. Work Package 6 Workshop Attendees

Organisation	Number of Attendees
CurrENT	1
European Policy Centre	1
EIA	1
ACER	1
ECB	1
JRC	1
Eurelectic	1
Ecologic	1
DG ENER	1
IRENA	1
ECCO	1
SolarPower Europe	1
DG ECFIN	1
DG TRADE	1
CMCC	1

Discussion

Project coordinator Zoi Vrontisi presented an introduction to the project, after which climate research director George Xexakis from HOLISTIC demonstrated the questionnaire section of the tool. Mentimeter was used to collect feedback from attendants on the relevance of sets of indicators specified for different thematic aspects (e.g., environmental aspects, or economic aspects). Participants indicated interest in understanding the sub-indicators underlying specific broader indicators such as “ecosystems and biodiversity”. This would enable better comments, according to the participants. It was explained that for certain indicators, such sub-indicators were available, but not for all. Subsequently, the model descriptions and model scenario results sections of the tool were demonstrated. Participants were interested to know to what extent users would have the possibility to change the scope and data granularity reflected in the tool. Finally, the drivers behind model functions and the impact analysis tool were presented. Participants asked how open-source the tool would be, and whether results would feed into other modelling work being implemented for the 2040 targets.

Project Takeaways

During the discussion about the model descriptions and scenario result functions, several participants hinted at the potential uses of merging these functions. If implemented, this would allow tool-users to understand which share of results would be driven by specific model elements and assumptions, which would be valuable new knowledge. Moreover, several participants highlighted that more information on sub-indicators would improve the questionnaire function of the tool. These are considerations that the DECIPHER team will take onboard in further developing the team, and aim to feed this back to the stakeholders, who will be invited for the demonstration webinar in the summer of 2025.

Work Package 7: Sustainability competences in university curricula

Date: 03/12/2024

Concept

The WP7 workshop on sustainability competencies aimed to foster dialogue between academia, policymakers, and experts on integrating sustainability into higher education programmes. The session brought together university representatives, modellers, and policymakers working on education and sustainability to examine the challenges universities face in embedding sustainability literacy, explore potential solutions, and define key competencies that students should acquire before graduating. A core focus was on stakeholder engagement—how collaboration between academia, policymakers, industry, and civil society can drive systemic change in sustainability education.

Attendees**Table 6.** Work Package 7 Workshop Attendees

Organisation	Number of Attendees
National Technical University of Athens	2
University of Salzburg	1
University of Gothenburg	1
Tampere University of Applied Sciences	1
University of Namur	3
Euro-Mediterranean Center on Climate Change	1
Institut Catholique d'Arts et Métiers	3
European Commission	1
Leiden University	1
University of Piraeus Research Center (UPRC)	2

Discussion

The workshop enabled collecting stakeholder feedback feeding into the White Book being developed by University of Deusto aiming to support the integration of sustainability competencies into university curricula, particularly for future policy makers in the areas of climate change and biodiversity. The White Book focuses on various competences related to sustainability, biodiversity, and climate policies. The Deusto University included several interactive in-workshop surveys to which participants were invited to contribute insights and recommendations, that will feed into the structure and content of the White Book.

The workshop centred around three key themes:

1. Identifying Core Competencies – Participants were asked to rank 15 sustainability-related competencies in terms of importance. The most highly ranked were critical thinking, systems thinking, and collaboration/collective action. Some disparities emerged in the ranking of competencies related to financial literacy and policy advice, with participants highlighting that competencies are interconnected rather than strictly hierarchical.
2. Institutionalization of Sustainability in Higher Education – The discussion explored the best practices for embedding sustainability into university structures. Key priorities included curricular planning, teacher training, participatory

methodologies, and governance reforms. The need for systemic integration of sustainability across disciplines rather than treating it as an "add-on" was emphasized.

3. Active Learning Methodologies – Various student-centred learning approaches were examined, including problem-based learning, challenge-based learning, and experiential learning. Participants stressed the need for practical application, emphasizing the importance of demonstrating sustainability in action rather than treating it as a theoretical subject. Several participants shared experiences from their institutions, highlighting barriers such as time constraints and faculty resistance.

Project Takeaways

Effective integration of sustainability competencies in university curricula requires a systemic approach rather than standalone courses, ensuring relevance across disciplines. Balancing theory with action is essential, emphasizing hands-on learning, critical reflection, and real-world applications. Institutional commitment is key, with governance structures, accreditation standards, and teaching methodologies aligned to support sustainability education. Teacher training and motivation must go beyond content knowledge and include effective pedagogy for sustainability literacy. Additionally, student involvement is crucial, with universities fostering peer-driven initiatives and community engagement to enhance impact. The White Book will incorporate stakeholder feedback related to policy recommendations, institutional strategies, and case studies in order to guide universities in embedding sustainability into curricula effectively.

3. Next Steps for Stakeholder Engagement

Building on the insights gathered from the targeted workshops, the next phase of the stakeholder engagement aspects of DECIPHER will focus on enhancing stakeholder participation through the Stakeholder Engagement Tool (T1.3) and developing a guidance document for methodologically improved policymaking (T1.4). The outcomes of the targeted workshops have highlighted the need for such accessible, transparent, and data-driven approaches to engage policymakers and the wider public in climate and environmental decision-making.

Under Task 1.3, the development of the stakeholder engagement tool will continue, ensuring it effectively supports policy assessment and public engagement. The tool will provide an interactive platform for stakeholders to engage with policy assessment by

expressing their priorities and perspectives on different policy dimensions. It will also offer visual representations to illustrate the broader socio-economic impacts of climate and environmental policies, making complex information more accessible and easier to interpret. The completed tool will be delivered as D1.3 “Stakeholder engagement tool”.

Building on Task 1.3, Task 1.4 will develop guidelines for methodologically improved and transparent public policy design and evaluation. This document will provide policymakers with practical steps to engage stakeholders effectively and integrate economic methods into decision-making. The guidelines will be informed by insights from previous tasks, ensuring a coherent and user-friendly manual for policymakers working on climate and environmental policies. The final output will be compiled in D1.4 “Guidelines for improved decision-making”. The guidelines will be further publicly disseminated through a policy brief, supporting the project’s broader objective of fostering transparent and well-informed policy processes.